

MAKSIMAL NOCHIZIQLI INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASI UCHUN CHEGARAVIY MASALA

Xolboyev Nurjon Abdujabbor o'g'li
Jizzax davlat pedagogika universiteti
E-mail: nurjonxolboyev96@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Impulsiv effektlar va maksimumlarga ega oddiy integro-differensial tenglamalarning birinchi tartibli sistemasi uchun nolokal chegaraviy masala o'rganildi. Chegaraviy masala integral shart bilan beriladi. Ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli, uni qisqartirib aks ettirish usuli bilan birgalikda qo'llaniladi. Chegaraviy masala yechimining mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlangan. Yechimlarning chegaraviy shartning o'ng tomoniga uzluksiz bog'liqligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: impulsiv integrodifferensial tenglamalar, nolokal chegaraviy shart, ketma-ket yaqinlashishlar, yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligi, yechimning uzluksiz bog'liqligi.

Masalaning qo'yilishi

$[0, T]$ segmentda chiziqli bo'lmagan integro-differensial tenglamaning quyidagi birinchi tartibli sistemasini ko'rib chiqamiz

$$x'(t) = f\left(t, x(t), \int_0^T \Theta\left(t, s, \max\{x(\tau) \mid \tau \in [\lambda_1 s; \lambda_2 s]\}\right) ds\right), \quad t \neq t_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (1)$$

nolokal chegaraviy shart

$$Ax(0) + \int_0^T K(t, s)x(s) ds = B(t) \quad (2)$$

va nochiziqli impulsiv ta'sir

$$x(t_i^+) - x(t_i^-) = I_i(x(t_i)), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p, \quad (3)$$

berilgan bo'lsin, bu yerda $0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_p < t_{p+1} = T$, $A \in R^{n \times n}$ matritsa, $K(t, s)$

$n \times n$ - o'lchovli matritsa funksiyasi va $\det Q(t) \neq 0$, $Q(t) = A + \int_0^T K(t, s) ds$,

$f: [0, T] \times R^n \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$, $\Theta: [0, T]^2 \times R^n \rightarrow R^n$, $I_i: R^n \rightarrow R^n$ berilgan funksiyalar;

$0 < \lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < 1$, $x(t_i^+) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^+} x(t_i + h)$, $x(t_i^-) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0^-} x(t_i - h)$ mos ravishda $x(t)$ funksiyaning $t = t_i$ nuqtadagi o'ng tomonli va chap tomonli limitlari.

$C([0, T], R^n)$ fazo $x(t)$, uzluksiz vektor funksiyalardan tashkil topgan Banax fazosini bildiradi, aniqlanish sohasi $[0, T]$, qiymatlar sohasi R^n va normasi

$$\|x\| = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |x_j(t)|}.$$

$PC([0, T], R^n)$ chiziqli vektor fazo quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$PC([0, T], R^n) = \left\{ x: [0, T] \rightarrow R^n; x(t) \in C((t_i, t_{i+1}], R^n), i = 1, \dots, p \right\},$$

bu yerda $x(t_i^+)$ va $x(t_i^-)$ ($i = 0, 1, \dots, p$) mavjud va chegaralangan; $x(t_i^-) = x(t_i)$.

$PC([0, T], R^n)$ chiziqli vektor fazoning Banax fazosidagi normasi quyidagicha:

$$\|x\|_{PC} = \max \left\{ \|x\|_{C((t_i, t_{i+1}])}, i = 1, 2, \dots, p \right\}.$$

Masalani yechilishi. $x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ funksiya barcha $t \in [0, T]$, $t \neq t_i$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$ lar uchun (1) integro-differensial tenglamani qanoatlantiradi, (2) nolokal integral shartni va $t = t_i$ $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$, $0 < t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_p < T$ lar uchun (3) nochiziqli limit shartini qanoatlantiradi.

Integral tenglamaga keltirish

$x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ funksiya (1)-(3) nolokal chegaraviy masalaning yechimi bo'lsin. U holda (1) tenglamani $t \in (0, t_{i+1}]$, intervalda integrallash orqali quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t f(s, x, y) ds &= \int_0^t x'(s) ds = [x(t_1) - x(0^+)] + [x(t_2) - x(t_1^+)] + \dots + [x(t) - x(t_i^+)] = \\ &= -x(0) - [x(t_1^+) - x(t_1)] - [x(t_2^+) - x(t_2)] - \dots - [x(t_i^+) - x(t_i)] + x(t). \end{aligned}$$

(3) shartni hisobga olib, oxirgi tenglikni quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$x(t) = x(0) + \int_0^t f(s, x, y) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)). \quad (4)$$

(4) dagi $x(t) \in PC([0, T], R^n)$ funksiya (2) chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantirishini ko‘rishimiz mumkin:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[A + \int_0^T K(t, s) ds \right] x(0) = \\ & = B(t) - \int_0^T K(t, s) \int_0^s f(\theta, x, y) d\theta ds - \int_0^T K(t, s) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) ds. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$\det Q(t) = \det \left[A + \int_0^T K(t, s) ds \right] \neq 0$ bo‘lgani tufayli (5) tenglikni qayta yozamiz

$$x(0) = Q^{-1}(t) \left[B(t) - \int_0^T K(t, s) \int_0^s f(\theta, x, y) d\theta ds - \int_0^T K(t, s) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) ds \right]. \quad (6)$$

(6) tenglikni (4) tenglikga qo‘yib, quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) = Q^{-1}(t) & \left[B(t) - \int_0^T K(t, s) \int_0^s f(\theta, x, y) d\theta ds - \int_0^T K(t, s) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) ds \right] + \\ & + \int_0^t f(s, x, y) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Quyidagi tengliklarni hisobga olib

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T K(t, s) \int_0^s f(\theta, x, y) d\theta ds &= \int_0^T \int_s^T K(t, \theta) d\theta f(s, x, y) ds, \\ \int_0^T K(t, s) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) ds &= \sum_{0 < t_i < T} \int_{t_i}^T K(t, s) ds I_i(x(t_i)), \end{aligned}$$

(7) tenglikdan quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$x(t) = Q^{-1}(t) B(t) - Q^{-1}(t) \int_0^T \int_s^T K(t, \theta) d\theta f(s, x, y) ds -$$

$$-Q^{-1}(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} \int_0^T K(t, s) ds I_i(x(t_i)) + \int_0^t f(s, x, y) ds + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)). \quad (8)$$

(8) tenglikda ba'zi soddalashtirishlardan so'ng quyidagi tengliklarga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t f(s, x, y) ds - Q^{-1}(t) \int_0^T \int_0^T K(t, \theta) d\theta f(s, x, y) ds = \\ = Q^{-1}(t) \int_0^t \left(A + \int_0^s K(t, \theta) d\theta \right) f(s, x, y) ds - \\ - Q^{-1}(t) \int_0^T \int_0^T K(t, \theta) d\theta f(s, x, y) ds; \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{0 < t_i < t} I_i(x(t_i)) - Q^{-1}(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < T} \int_0^T K(t, s) ds I_i(x(t_i)) = \\ = Q^{-1}(t) \sum_{0 < t_i < t} \left(A + \int_0^{t_i} K(t_i, s) ds \right) I_i(x(t_i)) - \sum_{t < t_{i+1} < T} Q^{-1}(t_i) \int_{t_i}^T K(t_i, s) ds I_i(x(t_i)). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

(9) va (10) tengliklarni (8) tenglikka qo'yib quyidagi tenglikga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) = J(t; x) \equiv Q^{-1}(t)B(t) + \sum_{0 < t_i < t} G(t, t_i) I_i(x(t_i)) + \\ + \int_0^T G(t, s) f \left(s, x(s), \int_0^T \Theta \left(s, \theta, \max \{ x(\tau) \mid \tau \in [\lambda_1 \theta; \lambda_2 \theta] \} \right) d\theta \right) ds \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

bu yerda

$$G(t, s) = \begin{cases} Q^{-1}(t) \left(A + \int_0^s K(t, \theta) d\theta \right), & 0 \leq s \leq t, \\ -Q^{-1}(t) \int_s^T K(t, \theta) d\theta, & t < s \leq T. \end{cases}$$

$$t \in (t_i, t_{i+1}], \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, p, .$$

(11) tenglama (1)-(3) masalani qanoatlantirishini tekshirish qiyin emas.

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